

Removal of Ni(II) from aqueous solutions by adsorption on nano-Fe₃O₄ : Kinetics and mass transfer study

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Abstract : The present study was undertaken to investigate the efficiency of nano-Fe₃O₄ (*n*-Fe₃O₄) for the removal of nickel from their aqueous solutions. Removal process of Ni(II) was carried out by using batch adsorption experiments. Various important process parameters such as concentration of metal solution, contact time, pH and temperature were investigated. It was observed that removal decreases from 90.48 to 87.94% by increasing concentration from 1.9×10^{-2} to 5.7×10^{-2} mol/L. pH studies revealed that basic ranges favour Ni(II) removal. Removal of Ni(II) by adsorption on *n*-Fe₃O₄ was found to be endothermic in nature. Kinetics of removal process has been studied and mass transfer coefficient and intra-particle diffusion constant were also calculated at different temperatures. The results of the present study suggest that *n*-Fe₃O₄ has high potential for the removal of Ni(II) and it can be used for nickel removal from aqueous solutions and Ni(II) rich industrial effluents as well.

Keywords : Adsorption, batch experiments, mass transfer study, nickel.

Introduction

Metals are very important in the development of any nation. Day by day, the amount of metals in water bodies is increasing due to release of metal rich effluents. Among various metals, Ni(II) is the 5th most abundant element in the world¹. Moreover, it has a wide spread application in various industries viz. electroplating units, battery manufacturing, paint formulation, porcelain enameling, mining and metallurgy²⁻⁴. These industries are the main sources of Ni(II) pollution. At lower concentrations, Ni(II) is not very harmful as it takes part in metabolic processes in the body but at higher concentrations, it shows harmful effects on flora and fauna⁵. Maximum permissible limit for Ni(II) in industrial wastewater is 2.0 mg/L³ but its presence in water bodies in higher amounts shows various toxic and harmful effects such as pulmonary fibrosis, renal edema, skin dermatitis, and gastrointestinal distress, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea^{5,6-9}. Hence, it is necessary to monitor the discharge of metal rich effluents and its treatment before being discharged. There are various treatment technologies such as solvent extraction,

reverse osmosis, extraction, precipitation, membrane separation, coagulation and adsorption which can be used for the removal of Ni(II) from aqueous solutions^{10,11}. Among these adsorption is a user friendly technology and it can remove the metallic pollutants more efficiently even at trace levels. In spite of these advantages it can also solve the problem of sludge disposal^{1,12-15}. Recently the application of nanoparticle as an adsorbent is receiving wide attention of several researchers for the removal of metallic pollutants from aqueous solutions¹⁶⁻¹⁸. In present study, nanoparticles of Fe₃O₄ has been synthesized and used as an adsorbent to investigate its adsorption efficiency for the Ni(II). Various important process parameters were optimized by using batch adsorption experiments. Intraparticle and mass transfer studies has been carried out to demonstrate kinetics of removal process.

Experimental

Preparation of adsorbent :

Adsorbent used in present investigation has been synthesised by co-precipitation of Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ salts.

Details of synthesis method has been given elsewhere¹⁹. After synthesis, adsorbent was characterized by using X-ray diffraction (XRD). Fourier Transform IR (FTIR) and TEM (Transmission Electron Microscopy). The Brunauer Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area, pore volume, and pore size distribution were investigated using a computer controlled automated porosimeter (Micromeritics ASAP 2020, V302G single port).

Batch adsorption experiments :

Stock solution of Ni(II) was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of NiSO₄·6H₂O in deionized water. Stock solution was diluted for getting required concentrations of working solutions. The ionic strength of the Ni(II) solutions was maintained at 1.0 × 10⁻² M NaClO₄. For pH adjustment, 0.1 M HCl/0.1 M NaOH solution was added as required. Removal studies were carried out by usual batch mode adsorption experiments by taking 50 ml of Ni(II) solution in 125 mL glass stoppered reagent bottles at desired concentration, pH, agitation speed and dose. Batch adsorption experiments were conducted at 25 °C (±0.5) on a shaking thermostat water bath. After adsorption experiments, adsorbent was separated by centrifugation (Remi 24, New Delhi, India). Remaining concentration of Ni(II) in aqueous solution was determined by UV-Vis spectrophotometer at 445 nm²⁰. Removal (%) of Ni(II) and amount of Ni(II) adsorbed on adsorbent were calculated by applying following formulas respectively :

$$\text{Removal (\%)} = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Amount adsorbed } (q_e) = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{M} \times V \quad (2)$$

where C_0 and C_e are the initial and equilibrium concentrations of Ni(II) (mol/L), M the mass of adsorbent (g) and V is the volume of solution (L), q_e is the amount adsorbed (mol/g).

Results and discussion

Characterization of the adsorbent :

Various characteristics of adsorbent is given in Table 1. It is clear from Table 1 that synthesized adsorbent is nanosized and has significant value of surface area. The phase present in synthesized nanoparticle was found to be

Table 1. Characterization of adsorbent

Phase	Fe ₃ O ₄
Particle diameter (nm)	15
BET surface area (m ² /g)	86.547
Porosity	0.27
Density (g/cm ³)	2.331
pH _{zpc}	7.1

Fe₃O₄ which was confirmed by its XRD. TEM results also support the XRD results (Figures not given).

Effect of contact time and concentration :

Concentration of Ni(II) solution was varied from 1.9 × 10⁻² mol/L to 5.7 × 10⁻² mol/L to study the effect of contact time and concentration. It was found that removal of Ni(II) increased from 87.94 to 90.48% by decreasing concentration from 5.7 × 10⁻² mol/L to 1.9 × 10⁻² mol/L (Fig. 1). It is also clear from Fig. 1 that only 120 min is sufficient for maximum removal after that there is not any further increase in removal of Ni(II). At lower initial concentrations, sufficient adsorption sites are available for the adsorption of metal ions. While at higher concentration the number of metal ions are relatively higher as compared to availability of adsorption sites.

Fig. 1. Effect of initial concentration and contact time on the removal of Ni(II) by adsorption on $n\text{-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$.

Effect of adsorbent dose :

Adsorbent dose strongly affects any removal process. Effect of adsorbent dose on the removal of Ni(II) were

Fig. 2. Effect of adsorbent dose on the removal of Ni(II) by adsorption on *n*-Fe₃O₄.

investigated by varying adsorbent dose from 2.0 to 20.0 g/L. It is clear from Fig. 2 that by increasing adsorbent dose removal increased from 80.95 to 100%. This trend is due to presences of higher active surface at higher adsorbent dose for fixed metal concentration.

Effect of pH on the removal of Ni(II) from aqueous solutions :

The pH of an aqueous solution has been reported an important process variable in the adsorption of metallic ions from aqueous solution onto the surface of any adsor-

bent. pH affects both the solubility of metal ions and degree of ionization²¹. The effect of pH was studied by varying the solution pH between 2.0 and 8.0 by keeping other experimental conditions constant. pH studies were not carried out beyond 8.0 to avoid Ni(II) precipitation. Fig. 3 depicts the effect of initial solution pH on the removal of Ni(II) at a fixed initial Ni(II) concentration of 1.9×10^{-2} mol/L. It is clear that the removal of Ni(II) by *n*-Fe₃O₄ is highly pH dependent. The removal efficiency of Ni(II) increased from 87.62 to 94.29% with the increase of the initial solution pH from 2 to 8.

Fig. 3. Effect of the pH on the removal of Ni(II) by adsorption on *n*-Fe₃O₄.

Fig. 4. Effect of temperature on the removal of Ni(II) by adsorption on $n\text{-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$.

Effect of temperature :

Temperature is another important parameter affecting adsorption processes. Batch experiments were performed under three different temperatures : 25, 35 and 45 °C to examine the effect of temperature on Ni(II) removal by $n\text{-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$. The results of the effect of temperature on Ni(II) removal are presented in Fig. 3. Removal of Ni(II) also increased from 90.48 to 96.19% by varying temperature from 25 to 45 °C (Fig. 4). This increasing trend confirms the endothermic nature of removal process.

Kinetic study :

Several kinetic models are available to understand the behavior of removal process of any adsorbate by adsorption process. In present study different types of kinetic models viz. pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order and intraparticle diffusion were used to investigate the mechanism of adsorption and rate controlling steps²². Mass transfer study was also carried out for better illustration of removal process.

Pseudo-first order kinetic model :

The first order rate equation of the Lagergren is given as follows²³ :

$$\log (q_e - q) = \log (q_e) - \frac{k_1}{2.303} t \quad (3)$$

where q_e and q are the amounts of Ni(II) ions on the adsorbent at equilibrium and at time t respectively (mg/g) and k_1 , is the pseudo-first order rate constant (min^{-1}).

The value of k_1 was determined from slope of the linear plots of $\log (q_e - q)$ vs t at different temperatures.

Pseudo-second order kinetic model :

The pseudo-second order equation is also based on the sorption capacity of the solid phase is given as follows^{24,25} :

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \frac{1}{q_e} t \quad (4)$$

$$h = k_2 q_e^2 \quad (5)$$

where k_2 is the second order rate constant (g/mg min), q_e is the adsorption capacity calculated by the pseudo-second order kinetic model (mg/g). The value of q_e and k_2 can be determined by the slope and intercepts of the straight line of the plots t/q_t vs t , respectively, h is known as initial sorption rate (Figure not given). The values of pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order rate constants for the removal of Ni(II) and at different temperatures are given in Table 2.

It is clear from Table 2, that value of k_1 increases by increasing temperature which confirms the endothermic nature of removal process. For pseudo-first order equation, experimental values of q_e did not agree with the calculated values obtained from the linear plots of pseudo-first order equation (Figure not given). While in the case of pseudo-second order equation, value of calculated q_e from pseudo-second order kinetics almost agreed well with the experimental values of q_e . On comparison of R^2

Table 2. Pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order rate constants for the removal of Ni(II)

Temp. (±0.5 °C)	Experimental <i>q_e</i> (mg/g)	Pseudo-first order model			Pseudo-second order model		
		<i>k</i> ₁ (× 10 ⁻² min ⁻¹)	<i>q_e</i> (mg/g)	<i>R</i> ²	<i>k</i> ₂ (g/mg min)	<i>q_e</i> (mg/g)	<i>R</i> ²
25	1.131	1.156	0.075	0.995	0.722	1.138	0.999
35	1.167	1.373	0.080	0.968	0.496	1.177	0.998
45	1.202	2.022	0.099	0.980	0.355	1.217	0.997

Fig. 5. Intraparticle diffusion plots for the removal of Ni(II) by adsorption on *n*-Fe₃O₄ at different temperatures.

value it can be revealed that pseudo-second order model can explain the system better way than pseudo-first order kinetic model.

Intraparticle diffusion study :

In many adsorption process adsorbate species may also transported from the bulk of the solution into the solid phase through an intra-particle diffusion process and it can be the rate-limiting step^{26,27}. Kinetic data were further analysed by intraparticle diffusion model. Value of rate constant of intraparticle diffusion *k*_{id} were calculated from the slopes of the linear portions of the plots of 'amount adsorbed vs square root of time' at different temperatures by using following equation²⁸.

$$q_t = k_{id} t^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

where *q_t* amount adsorbed at time *t* (mg/g), *t*^{1/2} the square root of the time (min^{1/2}). The values of *k*_{id} were calculated from the slope of curve at different temperatures from intraparticle diffusion plots (Fig. 5). Values of *k*_{id} at different temperatures are given in Table 3.

Mass transfer study :

In any adsorption process, a number of steps can take part. For any adsorption process, it is necessary to know

Table 3. Intraparticle diffusion rate constant for the removal of Ni^{II} by adsorption on *n*-Fe₃O₄ at different temperatures

Temp. (±0.5 °C)	Intraparticle diffusion rate constant <i>k</i> _{id} (× 10 ⁻³ mg/g min)
25	5.46
35	6.21
45	6.16

the extent of transfer of adsorbate from bulk to the surface of the solid adsorbent and at the interface of liquid and adsorbent particles. In present investigation, this probability was studied by using following mass transfer model²⁹.

$$\ln \left(\frac{C_t}{C_0} - \frac{1}{(1 + mk)} \right) = \ln \left(\frac{mk}{1 + mk} \right) - \left(\frac{1 + mk}{mk} \right) \beta_L S_s t \quad (7)$$

where *k* is a constant and is the product of Langmuir's parameters, *S_s* is the specific surface area, *β_L*, the coefficient of mass transfer, *m* is the mass of the adsorbent per unit volume. The values of *m* and *S_s* have been deter-

Fig. 6. Mass transfer plots for the removal of Ni^{II} by adsorption on *n*-Fe₃O₄ at different temperatures.

mined as follows :

$$m = \frac{W}{V} \tag{8}$$

$$S_s = \frac{6m}{d_p \delta_p (1 - \epsilon_p)} \tag{9}$$

where d_p is the diameter of adsorbent, ϵ_p is porosity of the adsorbent, and δ_p is the density of adsorbent.

Values of β_L , the coefficient of mass transfer, were calculated at different temperature by the slopes and intercepts of the plots of $\ln \left(\frac{C_t}{C_0} - \frac{1}{1 + mk} \right)$ vs t (Fig. 6) and the values coefficient of mass transfer are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Values of the mass transfer coefficient for the removal of Ni^{II} by adsorption on *n*-Fe₃O₄ at different temperatures

Temp. (±0.5 °C)	Coefficient of mass transfer $\beta_L (\times 10^{-5} \text{ cm/s})$
25	1.65
35	2.53
45	5.57

Conclusions :

On the basis of above studies following conclusions may be drawn.

(i) Adsorbent material used in present study has high potential for the Ni^{II}.

(ii) Removal of Ni^{II} increased by decreasing metal concentration form. Higher removal at low concentration is of industrial application.

(iii) pH studies revealed that in basic range *n*-Fe₃O₄ is highly efficient then in acidic range.

(iv) Adsorption of Ni^{II} on *n*-Fe₃O₄ was endothermic in nature. Higher removal can be achieved at higher temperature.

(v) Removal process was found to be governed by pseudo-second order kinetic.

(vi) Intraparticle diffusion constant k_{id} was calculated 5.46, 6.21 and 6.16 ($\times 10^{-3} \text{ mg/g min}$) respectively at three different temperatures.

(vii) Mass transfer constants were calculated to be 1.65×10^{-5} , 2.53×10^{-5} , 5.57×10^{-5} (cm/s) at 25, 35 and 45 °C.

The results of present investigation shows that *n*-Fe₃O₄ is highly efficient for the removal of Ni^{II} from aqueous solutions. The resultant data can be used as the baseline data for the treatment of Ni^{II} rich effluents.

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